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The Role of Employee Experience in Work-Life Balance Impacts on Well-Being¹

İş-Yaşam Dengesinin Esenlik Üzerindeki Etkisinde Çalışan Deneyiminin Rolü

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to determine whether employee experience has a mediating effect (partial or full mediation) on the impact of work-life balance on well-being. In order to achieve the research objective, quantitative relationship screening methods were used to examine these relationships between variables. The survey method was used as a data collection tool and analyses were conducted on data obtained from 479 employees using convenience sampling. Scales of work-life balance, well-being and employee experience were used as data collection tools. Initially, validity and reliability analyses of the scales were carried out. Correlation and regression tests were then used to test the research hypotheses.

As a result, firstly, a significant and positive relationship was found between work-life balance and both well-being and employee experience, and an explicit and positive relationship was found between well-being and employee experience. Furthermore, as a result of the regression analyses conducted to test the research question, it was concluded that the physical environment, the cultural environment and the technological environment, which are the sub-dimensions of employee experience, have a partial mediating role in the relationship between work-life balance and well-being. Based on the data from the study, it can be said that it is necessary for companies to invest in work-life balance and employee experience in order to improve employee well-being, and it would be healthy to develop human resource policies and practices in these areas.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Well-Being, Employee Experience.

ÖZET

Çalışmada iş yaşam dengesinin esenlik üzerindeki etkisinde çalışan deneyiminin aracı bir etkisi olup olmadığının (kısmi ya da tam aracı) ortaya koyulması amaçlanmıştır. Araştırma amacına ulaşabilmesi için değişkenler arasındaki bu ilişkilerin incelenmesinde niceliksel ilişki tarama metotları kullanılmıştır. Veri toplama aracı olarak anket yönteminden faydalanılmıştır ve kolayda örnekleme yöntemi 479 çalışandan elde edilen veriler üzerinden analizler gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırmada veri toplama aracı olarak iş-yaşam dengesi, esenlik ve çalışan deneyimi üzerine geliştirilmiş ölçeklerden yararlanılmıştır. Öncelikle ölçeklerin geçerlilik ve güvenilirlik analizleri yapılmıştır. Daha sonrasında araştırma hipotezlerini test etmeye yönelik olarak ise korelasyon ve regresyon testlerinden yararlanılmıştır.

Sonuç olarak öncelikle iş yaşam dengesiyle hem esenlik hem de çalışan deneyimi arasında anlamlı ve pozitif bir ilişki ve ayrıca esenlik ve çalışan deneyimi arasında da yine anlamlı ve pozitif bir ilişki bulunmuştur. Ek olarak araştırma sorusunu test etmeye yönelik olarak yapılan regresyon analizleri sonucunda ise iş yaşam dengesiyle esenlik arasındaki ilişkide çalışan deneyiminin alt boyutları olan fiziksel ortam, kültürel ortam ve teknolojik ortamın kısmi aracı rolü olduğu sonucuna ulaşılmıştır. Çalışmada elde edilen verilerden hareketle işletmelerin çalışanların esenliğini artırmaya yönelik olarak iş-yaşam dengesi ve çalışan deneyimine yatırım yapmalarının gerekliliği, bu alanlara yönelik insan kaynakları politika ve uygulamaları geliştirmelerinin sağlıklı olacağı söylenebilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İş-Yaşam Dengesi, Esenlik, Çalışan Deneyimi.

¹ This study is derived from the first author's Master's thesis titled The Role of Employee Experience in the Impact of Work-Life Balance on Well-Being, presented at Marmara University, Institute of Social Sciences, 2024.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the digitalization of the world, the conditions and expectations pertaining to the businesses are undergoing a process of continuous transformation. In conjunction with the evolving expectations and conditions of the modern working conditions, novel conceptual frameworks are emerging to address the changing factors influencing employee well-being. The traditional concept of the workplace is undergoing a period of transformation, driven by the differentiation of employee expectations in response to the digital revolution and the subsequent impact of these innovations. Consequently, employers are obliged to adapt their practices in order to retain their employees and attract those with the requisite qualifications to their organization. The most salient concepts pertinent to this subject matter in the contemporary era are work-life balance, well-being, and employee experience.

The traditional regulations of working life have been dismantled by the advent of remote working and flexible hours, which have become integral to the contemporary working experience, particularly during the pandemic. The ability of employers to achieve this equilibrium serves to enhance the appeal of their brands in the labor market. Besides this employee experience is a concept that is still evolving and remains a topic of ongoing discussion. Well-being and employee experience, which have gained prominence recently but are not yet well-represented in the literature. There is considerable research on the employee experience while fewer studies have examined the relationship between employee experience and well-being (Gabriel & Aguinis, 2022, Batat, 2022). Furthermore, the literature also contains studies on the impact of work-life balance on well-being (Lunau et al., 2014, Zheng et al., 2015). Given the dearth of studies on employee experience and well-being in the existing literature, this study aims to examine these concepts together with work-life balance, thereby contributing to the existing body of knowledge in this area.

The principal objective of this study is to ascertain whether employee experience exerts a mediating influence (either partial or full mediation) on the impact of work-life balance on well-being. A review of the literature revealed no studies that addressed all three variables simultaneously. Consequently, the research topic represents the core value of this study. In order to adequately address the predicted impacts, it is essential to gain a comprehensive understanding of the underlying concepts. From this perspective, the concepts of work-life balance, well-being and employee experience are first discussed in the study. The development of hypotheses is then explained, the relationships between the variables are examined, and suggestions are made in line with the results.

2. WORK-LIFE BALANCE

The concept of work-life balance is a phenomenon that emerged in the late 1970s to describe the relationship between work and personal life for mothers in Great Britain who wanted to return to the workforce. Since then, it has been frequently examined in studies in fields such as economics, psychology, sociology, gender and management (Smeltzer et al., 2016). In mid-1970, this concept was used for the first time, and the reason for the emergence of this concept is that there is a need for balance in the time spent outside of work, which is called free time, in order not to be interested in anything related to work and to live work and private life separately from each other, and this balance cannot be achieved. However, the inclusion of work-life balance in the literature has come to the agenda with the fact that work-life imbalance affects family life badly and people care about this issue (Akin et al., 2017). The idea that the time allocated to work should be restricted to ensure work-life balance dates back to the 1800s with the determination of weekly working hours. Another example from the past is the emergence of flexible working (maternity, breastfeeding leave, etc.) to enable women to participate in working life (Raja & Stein, 2014).

The concept of work-life balance is generally used to explain the demands of employees to be able to use their time resources sufficiently while planning their lives and the flexible policies offered by organizations to their employees. Individuals perceive this balance as freedom of choice and responsibility in their personal lives (Lewis & Beauregard, 2018). For most employees, family and work life have a decisive impact on overall life satisfaction. A person needs a balance between these two lives. Failure to achieve or disruption of this balance occurs when work has a negative impact on family life or family life has a negative impact on work life, resulting in conflict of roles (Giancaspro et al., 2023). More than one interrelated factor has had an indirect or direct impact on the emergence of this concept. These factors can be listed as economic, technological and political changes, changes in the perspective of gender in working life, changes in the perceptions of the workforce regarding work, and global competition (Maxwell &

McDougall, 2004). Today, work-life balance is considered as a concept related to the well-being of employees.

There have been various definitions of work-life balance from past to present. In 1993, Kofodimos defined work-life balance as a satisfying, healthy, productive life with work, play and love, while in 2000, Clark stated it as satisfaction and good functioning both at work and at home with minimal conflict of roles. In 2001, In 2006 Greenhaus, Allen and Spector, argued that this balance is related to the extent to which productivity and satisfaction in these roles are compatible with one's priorities in life. In 2007, Grzywacz and Carlson indentified it as the fulfillment of expectations in work and family roles. It is defined by Kalliath and Brough (2008) as an individual's perception of the balance between work and life outside of work. In 2011, Delecta suggested that it as the ability to fulfill one's work requirements as well as the requirements of non-work and family life. In summary, work-life balance can be defined as a person having a role and obtaining happy and satisfying experiences from their life while fulfilling this role. In work-life balance, each person's expectations and desires or methods of establishing balance may differ. For example, being married or single, financial situation, having children or not having children may cause expectations and wishes to differ. When these differentiated desires and expectations are met, a state of balance occurs (Drnovšek et al., 2024). Individuals personally determine their goals, objectives, demands or, in the simplest terms, what they want to achieve in both their work and non-work lives. Therefore, the balance for each individual, the requirements and expectations of the roles they have are formed in different ways. Work-life balance is related to the reconciliation of the roles that a person has throughout their life, achieving goals and being satisfied with every aspect of life. Work-life balance is the ability to conduct one's work life in harmony with dimensions other than work. These include social activities, home, family life, hobbies, interests, psychological and physical health (Kazmierska & Stankiewicz, 2016). The priority or importance of these dimensions varies among individuals.

While work-life balance refers to the balance between an individual's personal and professional life, it also directly affects the performance in these two areas. It significantly affects the performance of the employee in their work life. Excessive commitment to one side of these two lives will cause the balance to deteriorate as it will reduce the ability to deal with the other side. Working long hours with the ambition of promotion or success can disrupt the balance by reducing one's interest in other areas of life. Time and energy are limited resources therefore, an excessive interest in one area of life will take away from the person's time and energy in the other area. This decreases the level of satisfaction in the area in which the person's interest and time are cut. When work-life balance is achieved and sustainable, it will also improve the employee's work performance. Organizations that care about work-life balance have also realized that it has a positive impact on overall work performance and productivity of the organization. In cases where work-life balance is not achieved, it will cause negative effects on the overall productivity of the organization with the employee's dissatisfaction with their work and the resulting decrease in performance (Bhatti & Alnehabi, 2023).

2.1. Dimensions of Work-Life Balance

2.1.1. Work-Life Harmony

The concept of harmony is one of the definitions we frequently use in working life. Work-person and person-organization fit are important relationships in working life. Work-life harmony is the compatibility of the job with the person which means having the knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary to perform that job. The compatibility of the person with the organization can be defined as the common or similar values of the organization (Çırpan et al., 2019). In other words, the work-life harmony will be ensured by the compatibility of the person with both the work and the organization. If this harmony is achieved, it can be said that the employee will be less likely to face negative situations such as stress or distraction from work, as they will have sufficient knowledge and skills to do the job (Pamuk & Marşap, 2023). A large part of life is shaped around the work. So, it is crucial that the work is compatible with the person and their life (Dursun et al., 2016).

2.1.2. Neglecting Family Life

In ensuring work-life balance, it is important that the roles in one's work life and family life do not conflict or interfere with each other. The fact that the responsibilities of family and work life are in conflict with each other is a situation where the person cannot position these two roles in their life, cannot manage responsibilities, or one of them prevents the other from fulfilling (Altun & Yılmaz, 2016).

However, the absence of this conflict alone is not a factor of balance. In order to achieve this balance, these two roles should have minimal conflict with each other and the person should be satisfied with both work and family life (Aziz et al., 2016), and leisure time should be balanced between work life and life outside work. When the person can allocate time for professional and family responsibilities, the balance situation will become achievable (Costa et al., 2020).

The responsibilities and duties brought by these two lives may cause situations such as the interference of family life with work life or the inclusion of work life in the home environment as a result of the inability to separate the person's work and non-work life (Yavuz & Sağlam, 2018). Negativities in business life or reasons such as work being too busy, time and energy not being enough for the work carried out, prevent the person from fulfilling the responsibilities required by their role in family life, while reducing both the duration and quality of the time they devote to their family (Apaydın, 2011). Failure may also occur in working life when the duties and responsibilities in family life are too heavy for the person. Harmony and order within the family is one of the important factors affecting work-life balance (Savcı, 2015). The support given by the family to the person is a positive factor in the motivation necessary for the person to achieve their goals in working life (Rahim et al., 2020). The stress level of a person's work life can decrease with an understanding attitude of the family. Sharing housework is a factor that facilitates the achievement of a balance that alleviates the workload, especially for female employees (Topgül, 2016).

2.1.3. Time Allocation for Yourself

Working life is a big part of life. Since the situations as characterized good or bad that a person encounters in working life are related to the level of satisfaction in general, it can be said that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction.

How and in what way a person utilizes the remaining time outside of the tasks that they are responsible for fulfilling in working life, and whether they are free in making these plans are important factors for both work-life balance and life satisfaction. The person can utilize this planning time by resting, participating in a fun activity or doing something to improve themselves. These plans vary from person to person. Being able to plan and spend this free time outside of work by allocating it to oneself is one of the important factors affecting quality of life. This is related to the ability to spare time for oneself and to take care of oneself (Boylu & Paçacıoğlu, 2016). People need sufficient resources such as time, money, energy, etc. to rest and have fun and they meet their needs by using these resources. As a result, they obtain different satisfactions and one of the factors affecting human happiness is the achievement of these satisfactions (Koç, 1991).

2.1.4. Life as Work

The fact that life consists of work can occur physically or psychologically. It can be observed as the employee constantly thinking about work and being interested in work in their life outside of work. This may be due to the person's own will or due to reasons such as the inability to complete the duties and responsibilities of the job in the time allocated to work. This may occur because of the person's excessive attachment to the workplace and the job, or because the workload is too high. And this means that the person has a work-oriented mood in their life outside of work (Temel, 2006).

The concept of commitment can be defined as a state of mind in which there is a lively sense of belonging and a positive, satisfying attitude towards work. In situations such as the willingness to put more effort into the job and the management of challenges, the sense of dedication is characterized by factors such as feeling important, feeling proud. Being immersed in one's work causes the person to be able to concentrate completely on the work and thus time passes quickly, and to have difficulty in leaving the job because of the high sense of commitment and belonging.

The concepts of vitality and commitment are positive counterparts of burnout and cynicism. If the expectations from the workplace are high according to the time and quality of the person, the stress level of the person may increase as a high effort will be needed to meet this demand. Excessive stress in one's working life may result in depression, anxious mood or burnout (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004).

3. WELL-BEING

While the concept of well-being has been a major interest of philosophers and thinkers since the early ages of life, it began to be systematically analyzed in the 1950s and 1960s. The concept, which encourages living a good life, became even more interesting after World War II. After the war, it was observed that social well-being was encouraged by making people feel valued in order to recover from both physical and

moral damages caused by the war. Human welfare and well-being have been an important concern in psychological, philosophical and sociological fields in every period of life (Bornstein et al., 2003).

Studies on well-being emerged in the early twentieth century. In 1925, Flugel examined the emotional events experienced by people and their emotional reactions to these events. This study set an example for modern approaches to measuring well-being in daily life. After World War II, researchers started to conduct studies to measure people's happiness and life satisfaction. Today, well-being has become both a current and debated topic. Recently, regulations to increase the level of well-being of the person have been implemented in the business world. One of the main reasons for this is the realization that employees' well-being is also reflected in their working lives.

This concept was first defined in 1961 by Dr. Halbert L. Dunn as a state of mental and physical well-being (Bakan et al., 2022). The World Health Organization, on the other hand, defined well-being as a state in which a person has reached his/her potential, can cope with stress, is productive and contributes to society (Gürsoy & Sevin, 2021). This phenomenon can also be expressed as the level of satisfaction with one's general life, one's attitude and perspective towards life. From a philosophical point of view, the concept of well-being has a broader scope and can be defined as an individual's attitude towards whether their life is good or not. A person's well-being is actually what is good for them. The concept of well-being also deals with negative aspects. It can be expressed as the balance between good and bad phenomena in a person's life. In 2009, Hupper defined well-being as a positive and sustainable state that allows for the development of the individual, community or nation. Well-being can be defined as having a purpose, understanding, good social relationships, and psychological, social and physical opportunities to realize one's potential (Zoogah et al., 2023).

Well-being does not mean the same state for every individual. An adult and a child's perception of well-being will not be the same (Zalta et al., 2021). The goals that individuals want to achieve in life, or the things that make them happy, or the levels of happiness they will achieve from the same events are different. Individuals with very similar life conditions, social relationships and achievements may have very different levels of well-being. Well-being is also related to the level of satisfaction one receives from internal and external factors that affect one's life in general (TrongLuu, 2019). It can be expressed as a balance of positive and negative emotions that a person has. Factors such as the degree of satisfaction, love, and comfort are effective in the formation of these positive and negative emotions (Nieboer et al., 2005). The concept of well-being is related to the emotions, situations, behaviors and attitudes that a person achieves in the long term (Kolakowski et al., 2020).

3.1. Dimensions of Well-being

3.1.1. Happiness and Life Satisfaction

Happiness and the satisfaction and fulfillment felt from life in general is a factor affecting the well-being of individuals. It defines positive emotions that make an individual feel good and happy during life and negative emotions that make an individual feel pain and unhappiness. A point is reached as a result of the subjective evaluation of the individual's life satisfaction in well-being. For example, people with the same or similar life conditions may not have the same or similar level of life satisfaction. This is due to the fact that personal goals, desires and happiness levels vary from person to person (Kuzulu et al., 2013).

Living a happy life is one of the goals of individuals in life. As a result of the positive and negative emotions and situations felt during life, a person achieves a certain life satisfaction. This result can also be negative. If the positive side outweighs between these two emotional states of the person, well-being will be higher (Eryılmaz & Ercan, 2011). When people are happy, they generally have positive emotions. These positive emotions can be a factor for the person to be more active in life. As a result of being active, the possibility of being more successful can be positively affected (Irak, 2014).

Happiness and life satisfaction are different concepts. Happiness is a phenomenon that occurs when an individual reaches the goal of a certain target or when their needs are completed. The amount of effort the person spends to achieve this goal or to fulfill a need or a desire, or the magnitude of their determination and desire is also related to the degree of happiness. The realization of something a person has wanted for a long time may not make them as happy as if it had happened earlier. Failure to achieve one's wishes also leads to unhappiness. The concept of life satisfaction, on the other hand, is the achievement of positive emotions as a result of completing one's goals in life. Life satisfaction refers not only to the level of satisfaction or fulfillment obtained through an event, but also to the satisfaction that a person receives from life in general (Altun & Yılmaz, 2016). The fact that an individual's expectations from life and what they

have achieved in their current situation are in balance shows that they have a high life satisfaction (Fidanboy, 2019). The level of satisfaction with one's life, can be expressed as the attitude towards work and life outside of work (Dikmen, 1995). Since life is unpredictable and very comprehensive, there are many factors affecting life satisfaction. Some of these factors can be listed as the pleasure a person derives from daily routine tasks, seeing life as worth living, having a positive perception of their personality, feeling physically and mentally healthy, and the social environment the person has (Keser, 2005).

The fulfillment of employees' wishes and needs in terms of happiness and life satisfaction is an important factor for their performance in working life (Özavcı et al., 2022). For this reason, today's organizations have increased the importance and value they give to employees by changing their perspective on their employees in order to create competitive advantage. As a result, it would not be wrong to state that the working conditions offered to employees are affected in a good way. Improving working conditions will increase the job satisfaction of the employee and, in parallel, life satisfaction.

3.1.2. Mental and Physical Health

Although health is a broadly defined concept, it can be interpreted differently depending on the field in which it is used. Health status is also evaluated according to individuals' perceptions and cultures (Chappelle, 2000). Well-being and health are interrelated, but they do not mean the same thing. Health can be defined as a state and well-being as a process. At the same time, health is one of the many factors affecting well-being (Bağcıoğlu & Kaygın, 2018).

From a social perspective, the concept of well-being is closely related to education and health. Health is an element that may cause the individual to be concerned about well-being (Sabancı University Research Database, 2012). Since the degree to which an individual is healthy affects the life, it will also affect the well-being of the individual. This effect may vary according to the degree of physical or mental health.

The occurrence of conditions that will affect the living conditions of a person, such as illness or disability, is related to physical health. Deterioration of physical health may cause changes in the quality of life. This will cause the person to be unable to realize the things they plan and want to do on a daily basis or to realize their goals by spending more effort and time.

A person's mental and physical health is related to having the energy needed for the things they want to do during the day, regular physical and mental activity, and being able to rest after fatigue in order to feel vigorous (Mikušová et al., 2023). A person's psychological health is related to living a happy life. Psychological health is one of the factors of long-term well-being, which is not related to the immediate emotions of the person, but to the long-term emotional states and the extent to which the person can cope with emotions, situations and thoughts that affect the person negatively. Psychological health can be affected when negative emotions and situations increase in a person's life or when their duration is prolonged. Psychological health can be improved by establishing good relationships in life, feeling that one has a purpose, creating goals, realizing them and managing one's life. Good psychological health can also increase a person's resistance to emotions and situations that may affect them badly.

3.1.3. Meaning and Purpose

Since the existence of life, the individual's effort to make sense of life continues. People need life purpose and meaning in order to survive. Along with the purpose and meaning of life, the individual also questions the reason for their behaviors. As a result of this questioning process, they determine the purpose and meaning of life (Sezer, 2012).

A person's well-being also includes situations that are meaningful and satisfying for them. As a person achieves goals, it makes their life purpose more meaningful for them. People need meaning and purpose to do things in life. When a person feels that their life is meaningful and purposeful, well-being will be higher (Mikušová et al., 2023).

The things that the individual has experienced up to that moment, the perspective, beliefs and values acquired from the family culture are among the factors that affect the perception of life purpose and meaning. An individual's inability to find or make sense of the purpose and meaning of life is a source of stress. Because in life, individuals decide on their choices according to these values and beliefs and continue to live their lives with what they have gained or lost as a result of these choices (Güler et al., 2022). People need certain values, moral rules and choices in the form of right and wrong in order to conduct both their personal lives and social relations in society (Baş & Hamarta, 2015). As a result of these choices, they may be satisfied or unhappy with what they do.

3.1.4. Character and Virtue

The concept of character is a set of characteristics that begin to take shape with the birth of a person and give the person a sense of self (Eren, 1993). It can be defined as the characteristics that the person has from the moment of birth and that are difficult to change due to environmental factors. These characteristics also form the individual's predictions and expectations for the future (Eryılmaz & Ercan, 2011). People regulate their behaviors and attitudes with their character traits and adapt to their environment.

What is in one's mind and what one puts forth may not always be the same (Alkan, 2022). Character traits and the dimension of virtue are the attitudes, perceptions and behaviors of a person throughout their life. Character traits also affect individual's tendency to have positive or negative emotions. People may react differently to certain events and situations and have different feelings towards them. This means that it will also affect the general well-being of the person to different degrees. For example, extroverted people are more likely to be active, social and have positive emotions in life than introverts (Korkmaz, 2021). Being an extrovert may cause an individual to have more social needs than an introvert. Compared to an introvert, they may need their circle of friends more or may enjoy the time they spend with friends much more. A negative or positive situation does not affect everyone's well-being to the same degree. This is why the concepts of character and virtue have different effects on well-being for each individual.

3.1.5. Close Social Relationships

Social needs, which come after the physiological and safety needs in Maslow's hierarchy of needs, include needs such as belonging to a group, acceptance, and social relations. Social needs arise when people are able to meet their physiological needs and feel safe.

With the birth of a person, their close and social environment begins to form. While this may include mother, father, relatives and neighborhood friends in infancy, it expands in adulthood with social relationships such as work colleagues and close friends. These social relationships cover a large part of a person's life. The roles that people acquire in life and the roles they give to the people around them in their lives and the degree of importance of the relationship between these two roles vary according to the size of the relationship. The state of one's social relations is a factor of well-being. People can use their social relationships as a tool to reduce stress and increase well-being (Mikušová et al., 2023). A person's higher well-being is also effective in establishing more positive and healthy relationships. Individuals with a higher level of well-being are more likely to offer insights that are important in bilateral relationships such as patience and positivity to the other party. People with higher well-being are also more capable of establishing closer relationships (Günaydın & İnal, 2022).

When an employee feels lonely in the organization, it affects their sociality. With the support received from coworkers, it can make it easier for the employee to overcome work-related problems or to feel more emotionally comfortable by sharing their problems. It can be said that feeling lonely will reduce the level of well-being and satisfaction with work and life (Tortumlu & Taş, 2020). Social support also has a positive effect on coping with stress. People can receive social support from the institution they work, friends, family, any community or pet. Although this support does not occur verbally or in the form of behavior, it is effective even if the person feels the presence of support (Xi et al., 2018).

3.1.6. Financial and Material Stability

In working life, wage is one of the factors that concern the employee the most. People receive a wage as a result of the work they do, the labor they put forth and meet their needs with this tool. (Ataay, 1988) Money is a resource that a person needs in order to survive. It is also a tool that affects the comfort, well-being and quality of life. According to the abundance or scarcity of this resource, a person's living conditions are shaped. People work in order to have this resource and to sustain their lives. The fact that a person works only to earn money also affects the satisfaction they get from working life. In addition to this purpose, studies have shown that when people find their work meaningful or enjoy their work, their welfare level will be higher (Alparslan et al., 2022).

An individual's material and financial situation is highly influential on their happiness and life satisfaction. A person's high-income level will expand the range of goods and services that they can benefit from in their life, and they will have the opportunity to choose the one that is better for them. When they obtain what is better for themselves, the level of satisfaction may be higher (Acar, 2019). Determining the level of welfare related to financial situation is also related to the ability to maintain the current standard of living.

Being satisfied with one's desired standard of living and being able to financially meet one's wants and needs can be given as an example of financial well-being (Mikušová et al., 2023).

4. EMPLOYEE EXPERIENCE

Although employee experience is a relatively new concept, it has been used quite frequently. The emergence of the concept is due to factors such as easy accessibility of information, changing characteristics and thoughts of people with the changing world, the development of technology day by day and globalization (Morgan, 2017). Employee experience is based on the employee's relationship with factors such as other employees, policies and working conditions within the organization (Elmin & Ulaştrın, 2023) and covers the process from the moment the person starts to work until the moment they leave the job. With the emergence of employee experience, employers are trying to adapt to this understanding in order to remain in the market, increase their reputation, attract and retain qualified labor force. The concept was defined by Plaskoff in 2017 as all of a person's perceptions about their relationship with the organization (Gerçek, 2022b). People are in a relationship with the company they work for, but the influencing or affected elements of this relationship are not only the employee and the organization. The employee's perception of the organization that emerges as a result of all the interactions of this relationship is related to the employee experience. While the general structure of the organization affects the employee experience, a manager in the organization can also affect the experience process of the employee in his team. Therefore, interactions within the organization are also one of the important factors affecting employee experience (Coyle-Shapiro & Shore, 2007). Employee experience is the perceptions of employees as a result of their colleagues, managers, service recipients, job description, tools and resources they need while doing the job (Rasca, 2018). Whitter (2019) on the other hand, defines this concept as from candidacy to retirement.

Employee experience encompasses the totality of employees' psycho-cognitive feelings towards work. These are feelings related to organizational culture, colleagues and work environment. It can be said that with a positive employee experience created by these emotions, employee satisfaction, commitment to the organization and as a result, overall performance will be positively affected. In order to design an effective employee experience, it is necessary to create a working environment that supports and encourages the employee's work-related experiences. It is thought that the overall success of the organization will increase by considering, meeting or supporting both the emotional and social needs of the employee. With this idea, the traditional perception of increasing the employee's commitment to the organization is replaced by a whole employee-oriented experience process. Therefore, employee experience is actually an important design process for the overall success of the organization (Abhari et al., 2023). The positive outcomes of this experience can be manifested as increased motivation, job satisfaction and performance (Giancaspro et al., 2023).

Employee experience is more about the employee's perspective as opposed to the attitude of the organization in the process of solving the problems faced by the people or the organization. The employee observes and questions this process, analyzes it, and as a result, a perception of the organization is formed. It has recently become a factor that arouses the desire to work in the organization, especially for the young workforce (Lee & Kim, 2023). While employers used to care only about employee loyalty and long-term employment, today this perception is increasingly being replaced by employee experience. Employee experience is a perspective where the employee is at the focal point, which is viewed from a larger perspective than employee engagement. While employee engagement is thought of as participation in the organization's decisions about policies, processes and practices that will affect employees and their work, in employee experience, employees are central to the design of this process. While employee engagement involves a shorter-term planning, employee experience refers to a long-term design that covers the whole process (Panneerselvam & Balaraman, 2022). In order to keep up with the ever-changing world, it is important for employers in every field to adapt to change (Morgan, 2020). With the correct planning organizations can become the preferred employer and the desired workplace (Padhi & Joshi, 2022).

Employee experience is a different process for each individual. Since people are beings who act and think with their emotions and attitudes, it can be said that this process causes different expectations, desires and needs from person to person (Farndale & Kelliher, 2013). Since each individual has different attitudes and behaviors, it is a challenging process for organizations to design this process. The priorities that each individual cares about and values may be different. Organizations need to analyze their employees and feed on these analyses to design the employee experience and once designed, it needs to be sustainable (Morgan, 2017). This design includes determining the steps in the process from the recruitment to the last

interaction of the employee in the process of leaving the job and meeting the wishes of the organization and the employee while determining these steps (Yohn, 2020).

4.1. Dimensions of Employee Experience

4.1.1. Physical Environment

The environment in which people live is an important factor affecting their emotional state (Bilgin, 1995). Employees establish an emotional bond with the place where they work (Rothe et al., 2015). The majority of white-collar workers spend approximately 40 hours a week in the office environment. In some studies, it has been suggested that the working conditions of the office, such as the temperature or coldness, the airiness, the degree of illumination and light, affect the person psychologically, socially and physically (Hoşten & Dalbay, 2018). With the development of technology, new working environments have emerged. Businesses seek changes in working environments due to important factors such as flexibility and cost. The working environment affects employees' work-related experiences. As a result of this effect, it is possible to say that the working environment is an effective factor on behavior, attitude and performance. The conditions of the work environment are also seen as a symbol of organizational identity. In order for the work environment to have a positive impact on employee experience, it is also important that the workplace design reflects the organizational culture (Gerçek, 2022a).

Situations where the working environment is not suitable can become a source of stress. The fact that a person is working in a poorly designed work environment may cause them to get tired more easily, their performance may be badly affected, or they may feel bad and feel the need to get away (Can et al., 2015). In order to provide the focus for employees they need it is necessary to create a comfortable working environment. Therefore, the physical environment should be considered as the center of employee experience, not an office (Morgan, 2017).

4.1.2. Technological Environment

With the technological developments, new working conditions have emerged and the technological experience of employees has become a remarkable element (Abhari et al., 2023). The competitive opportunities of businesses that do not follow technological developments continuously, cannot keep up with change or cannot make a difference by developing the technology they have, are negatively affected in the market. Organizations that are open to innovation and change should have employees empowered with technology (Daft, 2015).

Morgan (2018) described the technological environment as the central nervous system of the organization. Building on this definition, a study published by Josh Bersin Company (2021) supported the idea that technology is an important factor for the employee experience to become sustainable. Technology has an impact that supports other sub-dimensions of the organization (Moganadas, 2022) and is one of the most primary factors that support the long-term development of businesses. Human resources practices that change with the development of technology are one of the advantages in daily working life. The software and devices used by companies are within the scope of the technological environment. Together with these applications, jobs become easier and the motivation can increase. Employers should consider technological opportunities while shaping employee experience designs (Chandwani et al., 2021).

To see the technological opportunities provided at the workplace, one can look at whether these opportunities are offered to all employees. It is also important whether these opportunities are tools that would be preferred to use in personal life. In other words, it is ideal if the technological tools offered by the workplace are products that we would prefer to use in our personal lives. Offering products used as consumers in business life can be an important factor for technological experiences. Another important issue is that the opportunities offered should be at a level that meets the employee's wishes and needs rather than their quantity and quality. Achieving this balance will be an important element both to improve the employee experience and to use financial resources correctly (Morgan, 2018).

4.1.3. Cultural Environment

Deal and Kennedy (1982) define organizational culture as a regulator of behavior, while Wilkins and Ouchi (1983) define it as a set of perceived meanings that have validity within a particular group and time period. Organizational culture can be defined as the influence of values, norms, behaviors, beliefs, traditions, customs and relationships between people that affect the process of carrying out the work and the results that emerge after the completion of this process. In short, organizational culture can be summarized as the social values, standards, norms, beliefs and understandings created and shared among

the people. Organizational culture is affected by employees and employees are affected by organizational culture since it is people who create and are affected by the culture within the organization (Özkalp et al., 2006).

Cultural environment is another sub-dimension of employee experience that is different from physical and technological environment. An example of this is the excitement the employee feels when going to work or the bad feelings they have when they do not want to go to work.

In order to provide a good experience for employees in a cultural environment, the culture should prioritize employee well-being, senior managers should be in a relationship with employees as coaches or mentors, employees should be treated fairly, the necessary resources for learning and development should be offered and encouraged to employees. There should be a structure that includes differences within the organization and supports participation, employees should feel part of the organization and the organization should have reasonable goals and objectives. Everyone should feel valued within the organization, and the reputation of the organization should be in a positive position for employees and society (Başaran, 2021).

Morgan (2017) defines the cultural environment simply as the perceptions and values that are held to create emotions and lists the characteristics that should be possessed to create a good organizational culture as follows; the company has a positive image, employees feel valued, the organization has a legitimate purpose, vision and mission, employees see themselves as part of the team, employees make suggestions for the development of the culture, the organization is able to provide the necessary resources to learn and implement new things, justice is ensured within the organization, and the well-being and health of employees are considered while creating the culture.

5. RESEARCH MODEL AND HYPOTHESES

The main problem of the research model is to answer the question "Does employee experience have a mediating role in the effect of work-life balance on well-being?". As a result of the literature research conducted for this model, research hypotheses were established as follows.

5.1. The Relationship between Work-Life Balance and Employee Experience

One of the major reasons why the concept of work-life balance has become popular in recent years is the increasing importance given to employee experience and the initiatives of businesses to work in this field (Maxwell, 2005). Especially with the pandemic period, there have been changes in policies that will positively affect the employee experience. The competitiveness of companies that make their employees feel valuable also increases. Businesses that are aware of this know that a good employee experience design must be made in order to offer this balance to employees. A successful employee experience design should also be compatible with the culture of the organization. If it is compatible, this process will become consistent and sustainable. The policies and practices of the organization can be in a supportive position for this balance to occur or become sustainable. On the contrary, culture can also be the main element of not achieving this balance (Guest, 2002). In cases where the balance is not achieved, the motivation of the person related to the job also decreases. This leads to consequences such as not to feel belonging and not want to work. Thinking that one cannot achieve work-life balance is one of the important factors affecting the employee experience. If a person cannot be satisfied with their life outside of work because of work, it will not be possible to expect them to have good feelings about work. Therefore, it is predicted that work-life balance affects employee experience.

H1: Work-life balance affects employee experience.

5.2. The Relationship between Work-life balance and Well-being

The effort of employees to fulfill different roles in life causes physical and psychological stress. Decisions taken in work and non-work life without taking into account these different roles and the established order negatively affect the balance in the person's life (Genç et al., 2016). In cases where work-life balance cannot be achieved, negative behaviors, physical or psychological problems may occur. When people cannot achieve work-life balance, they have difficulty in fulfilling different roles in terms of time and energy (Kurtuluş et al., 2023) and it affects the well-being. Employees who can maintain work-life balance in their lives are more likely to be happy, healthy and have a higher performance than employees who cannot achieve this balance. Work-life balance also has an impact on overall life satisfaction. Life satisfaction is one of the sub-dimensions of well-being. Therefore, it is possible to say that there is a direct relationship between work-life balance and well-being. As a result of work-life imbalance, a person's life satisfaction level may decrease. Failure to achieve work-life balance leads to a decrease in the person's

performance, job satisfaction, life satisfaction and quality. Failure to achieve this balance also causes the person to be under intense stress as it requires them to spend even more effort to achieve balance, and their psychological and physical health and well-being are affected (Altıntaş & Altıntaş, 2023).

Research on the impact of work-life balance on well-being indicates that when the roles of a person's life are in a state of balance, the level of satisfaction from their general life may be higher and their general health may be better (Toker & Kalıpçı, 2022). In various studies in the literature, it is stated that work-life balance affects job performance, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, as well as employee health, family life and life satisfaction. Work-life imbalance that occurs with the conflict of roles negatively affects these factors that affect the well-being of the individual (Sirgy & Lee, 2018). Based on these explanations, it is possible to predict that work-life balance has an impact on well-being.

H2: Work-life balance affects well-being.

5.3. Mediation Relationship of Employee Experience

Experiences at work have a decisive impact on well-being and well-being is related to the employee experience and how healthy and good this experience process is. The employee experience process can affect well-being both positively and negatively (Sutton & Atkinson, 2023). Employees who have positive work-related experiences are likely to have higher work-related well-being (Tuomi & Vanhala, 2006). When it comes to well-being, it will be important that the arrangements in the employee experience support this process so that the person can struggle with the negative emotions and situations they encounter in life. In addition, a well-designed employee experience process will become a factor that affects job satisfaction and happiness levels by enabling people to benefit from talent acquisition and learning opportunities (Başaran & Ünal, 2021). The relationship between well-being and employee experience is becoming increasingly important in terms of employee retention (Rasca, 2018). As a result, considering the possible impact of work-life balance and employee experience on well-being, it is predicted that employee experience may have a mediating effect in this triple relationship.

H3: Employee experience mediates the relationship between work-life balance and well-being.

6. METHOD

6.1. Sample of the Study

The population of the study consists of white-collar employees. The survey data for the research were obtained by convenience sampling method between 22.12.2023-28.03.2024. The survey questionnaire was delivered to white-collar employees via LinkedIn and WhatsApp. As a result of the research, 495 people were reached. Considering the situations that were not suitable for the purpose of the research, 16 answers were excluded from the data results and as a result, the data obtained with the participation of 479 people were analyzed. In summary, 56.8% of the participants were female and 43.2% were male. 60.5% of the participants are between the ages of 25-34. The least number is in the 55 and over age group. The most common answer to the working period in the organization was 0-5 years with a rate of 75.8%. 1.9% of the participants have been working at the same workplace for 24 years or more. It is seen that most of the participants work in the service sector with a rate of 61.6%.

6.2. Data Collection Tools

In the first part of the research questionnaire, demographic questions were asked to the participants, in the second part, the Work-Life Balance Scale developed by Apaydın (2011) together with expert opinions was used. The scale consists of four dimensions, 20 questions, including work-life harmony, neglecting family life, time allocation for yourself, and life as work, and a five-point Likert scale was used. In the third part of the questionnaire, the Well-being Scale developed by VanderWeele (2017) was used. The scale consists of six dimensions including happiness and life satisfaction, mental and physical health, meaning and purpose, character and virtue, close social relationships, and financial and material stability. There are two items under each dimension and 12 questions in total. The scale rating is a 10-point Likert scale. In the fourth and final part, the Employee Experience Scale developed by Morgan (2017) was used to measure employee experience. The 5-point Likert-type scale consists of 17 questions and 3 dimensions as, physical, psychological and technological environments.

6.3. Reliability of the Scales

Table 1 shows the data on the reliability analysis of the scales conducted in the study calculated with Cronbach's Alpha value.

Table 1. Reliability Analyses of Work-Life Balance, Well-being and Employee Experience Scales

Variables	Number of Articles	Cronbach Alpha (α) Values
Work-Life Balance	20	0,910
Work Life Harmony	6	0,880
Neglecting Family Life	6	0,856
Time Allocation for Yourself	4	0,734
Life as Work	4	0,736
Well-being	10	0,751
Happiness and Life Satisfaction	2	0,870
Meaning and Purpose	2	0,692
Mental and Physical Health	2	0,648
Financial and Material Stability	2	0,747
Close Social Relationships	2	0,860
Employee Experience	17	0,941
Physical Environment	4	0,758
Cultural Environment	10	0,933
Technological Environment	3	0,818

As seen above, all dimensions of the work-life balance scale and the employee experience scale are above the Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.7 and the scales are considered reliable.

In the 12-question and 6-subdimension well-being scale, the Cronbach's Alpha value of the character and virtue sub-dimension was determined as 0.258. Therefore, two items in the character and virtue sub-dimension were removed from the analysis. Then, Cronbach's Alpha value was calculated as 0.751 and the scale was accepted as reliable. Therefore, the new form of the scale consists of 5 sub-dimensions.

6.4. Validity of the Scales

First the results of KMO (.915) and Barlett's tests (X^2 4526,199, df 190, p ,000) of the work-life balance scale were analyzed and the scale was found to be suitable for factor analysis. As a result of the factor analysis, four factors emerged as in the original scale and it was found that the factor loadings are between the values as follows; for work life harmony (.553-.891), for neglecting family life (.607-.752), for time allocation for yourself (.499-.792) and for life as work (.449-.812).

As mentioned above, as a result of the reliability analysis, one of the sub-dimensions of the well-being scale (character and virtue) was excluded from the analysis and the subsequent analyses were carried out with this new scale structure. The results of KMO (.828) and Barlett's tests (X^2 2347,588, df 45, p ,000) of the well-being scale were analyzed and the scale was considered to be favorable for factor analysis. The components of the five-factor structure that emerged as a result of the factor analysis are happiness and life satisfaction (.863-.893), meaning and purpose (.679-.799), mental and physical health (.528-.909), financial and material stability (.588-1,013) and close social relationships (.855-.883).

Finally, the results of KMO (.954) and Barlett's tests (X^2 5085,026, df 136, p ,000) of the employee experience scale were analyzed and the scale was found to be suitable for factor analysis. The analysis revealed the following three factors as in the original scale and the factor loadings were within the ranges indicated; physical environment (.638-.727), cultural environment (.621-.846), and technological environment (.678-.833).

7. FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH

The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, and the kurtosis and skewness coefficients of the variables show that the data have a normal distribution. The mean and median values are generally close to each other and histogram plots are also in the form of a normal distribution.

7.1. Correlation Analysis

The relationships between the variables were determined by Pearson Correlation analysis and the values are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation Values of Variables

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1. Work-Life Balance	1														
2. Work-Life Harmony	,754*	1													
3. Neglecting Family Life	-,875*	-,480*	1												
4. Time Allocation for Yourself	,753*	,374*	-,617*	1											
5. Life as Work	-,787*	-,479*	,613*	-,487*	1										
6. Well-being	,417*	,0362*	-,329*	,332*	-,300*	1									
7. Happiness and Life Satisfaction	,476*	,368*	-,408*	,407*	-,136*	,766*	1								
8. Meaning and Purpose	,422*	,353*	-,361*	,359*	-,105*	,753*	,661*	1							
9. Mental and Physical Health	,428*	,367*	-,315*	,358*	-,142*	,734*	,626*	,587*	1						
10. Financial and Material Stability	,221*	,144*	-,208*	,230*	-,119*	,264*	,154*	,156*	,133*	1					
11. Close Social Relationships	,369*	,314*	-,299*	,302*	-,079	,730*	,525*	,456*	,444*	,021	1				
12. Employee Experience	,423*	,383*	-,326*	,384*	-,249*	,390*	,405*	,423*	,372*	,171*	,330*	1			
13. Physical Environment	,307*	,293*	-,228*	,269*	-,183*	,258*	,268*	,287*	,247*	,108*	,205*	,836*	1		
14. Cultural Environment	,440*	,391*	-,341*	,405*	-,186*	,403*	,429*	,439*	,383*	,188*	,348*	,967*	,715*	1	
15. Technological Environment	,300*	,274*	-,235*	,265*	-,144*	,316*	,299*	,330*	,307*	,111*	,266*	,790*	,559*	,688*	1

* Correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$ level.

According to the results of the analysis conducted to determine the relationship between work-life balance, well-being and employee experience, there is a negative relationship between work-life balance, well-being and employee experience with the factors of work-life balance as neglecting family life and life as work. Also, there is a positive and strong relationship between these two factors.

7.2. Regression Analysis

Simple regression analysis was conducted to determine the effect of work-life balance on employee experience. The results obtained are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Regression Values for the Effect of Work-Life Balance on Employee Experience

Independent Variables	Unstandardized β	Standard Error	β	t Value	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
(Fixed)	23,261	3,284	-	7,083	,000	-	-
Work-Life Balance	,465	,046	,423	10,193	,000	1,000	1,000
F				103,900			
Adjusted R2				,177			
R2				,179			
Estimated Standard Error				14,29343			
Significance Level				,000			

* Dependent variable: Employee Experience

According to the results, work-life balance has a significant ($0.000 < 0.05$) effect on employee experience and so hypothesis H1 is accepted.

The data of the simple regression analysis conducted to determine the effect of work-life balance on well-being is given in Table 4.

Table 4. Simple Regression Analysis Results for the Effect of Work-Life Balance on Well-being

Independent Variables	Unstandardized β	Standard Error	β	t Value	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
(Fixed)	42,853	2,551	-	16,799	,000	-	-
Work-Life Balance	,354	0,035	,417	10,009	,000	1,000	1,000
F				100,181			
Adjusted R2				,172			
R2				,174			
Estimated Standard Error				11,10312			
Significance Level				,000			

* Dependent variable: Well-being

According to the data obtained, the effect of work-life balance on well-being is significant ($p < 0.05$) and H2 is accepted.

Table 5 presents the regression analysis results regarding the mediating role of employee experience and its factors.

Table 5. Multiple Regression Analysis for the Mediating Role of Employee Experience and its Factors in the Effect of Work-Life Balance on Well-Being

Model	Unstandardized β	Standard Error	β	t Value	Sig.
1	(Fixed)	42,583	-	16,799	,000
	Work-Life Balance	,354	,417	10,009	,000
2	(Fixed)	38,166	-	14,721	,000
	Work-Life Balance	,261	,038	,307	6,903
	Employee Experience	,201	,034	,260	5,859
3	(Fixed)	40,117	-	15,104	,000
	Work-Life Balance	,317	,037	,379	8,606
	Physical Environment	,415	,125	,144	3,316
4	(Fixed)	38,971	-	15,345	,000
	Work-Life Balance	,252	,038	,297	6,640
	Cultural Environment	,332	,054	,273	6,111
5	(Fixed)	38,869	-	14,839	,000
	Work-Life Balance	,301	,036	,354	8,300
	Technological Environment	,800	,163	,210	4,919

* Dependent variable: Well-being

Multiple linear regression analysis was performed to determine the mediating role of employee experience in the effect of work-life balance on well-being. Result of analysis showed that when the significant relationship between work-life balance and well-being was evaluated together with the employee experience, the significance of the relationship did not deteriorate but the effect reduced. According to this result, it is concluded that employee experience has a partial mediating role in the effect of work-life balance on well-being. In addition, the mediation effect of the physical, cultural and technological environment was also examined and the significant effect of work-life balance on well-being decreased in all three analyzes. Therefore, it is concluded that H3 is accepted as all three sub-dimensions of employee experience have a partial mediating role in the relationship between work-life balance and well-being.

8. CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the objective was to ascertain the role of employee experience in the effect of work-life balance on well-being. To this end, a correlation analysis was conducted initially. The results of the analysis indicated a significant and positive relationship between work-life balance and well-being, which is in accordance with the hypothesis. It can be posited that those who achieve a state of work-life balance tend to exhibit an increase in their well-being, or that as the level of well-being rises, work-life balance rises in parallel. It can therefore be posited that increasing the pleasure individuals derive from their lives, facilitating the realization of their life goals, cultivating healthy social relationships and prioritizing both mental and physical health will prove an efficacious strategy for enhancing work-life balance. The results of the regression analysis between these two variables indicate that work-life balance has a significant effect on well-being. In light of these findings, it can be posited that establishing appropriate work priorities, attaining a balance between work and personal life, and ensuring work-life balance are effective strategies for enhancing individual well-being.

Another outcome is that the sub-dimensions of neglecting family life and having a life consisting of work are positively correlated with one another, while they are negatively correlated with the other three variables and all sub-dimensions. This result is to be expected, given that these two sub-dimensions are negative. This demonstrates that individuals who dedicate an excessive amount of time to their work, work continuously, and prioritize their professional lives to the detriment of their personal and familial

obligations, ultimately experience a sense of being overwhelmed. The negative correlation between these two sub-dimensions and all other dimensions indicates that individuals who are work-oriented and neglect their personal lives have difficulty achieving a healthy work-life balance. This negatively affects their well-being and leads to a negative experience as an employee.

The analysis of the interaction between work-life balance and employee experience revealed a positive and significant relationship between both variables and all other sub-dimensions, with the exception of the sub-dimensions of neglecting family life and life as work. Furthermore, the results indicated that work-life balance has a positive effect on employee experience. In other words, it can be posited that the employee experiences of those who provide work-life balance are positively affected.

The analysis conducted to determine the mediating role of employee experience in the effect of work-life balance on well-being revealed that the employee experience and its sub-dimensions of physical environment, cultural environment and technological environment have a partial mediating role in the effect of work-life balance on well-being. It can therefore be concluded that employee experiences have an important role in increasing the well-being of individuals who provide work-life balance.

In light of these findings, it can be posited that organizations should prioritize an understanding of the significance of work-life balance and provide their employees with the necessary support in this regard. Despite the inevitable tension between work and personal life, it is crucial to implement human resources policies that mitigate or facilitate a harmonious balance between the two. It is crucial to align the necessity for maintaining work-life balance with the evolving qualifications, demands and expectations of the labor force. It is vital that employers and professionals provide this necessity in a comprehensive manner to the workforce, which encompasses individuals with diverse characteristics and expectations. Failure to achieve an equilibrium between one's professional and personal lives, an inability to fulfill one's roles in both domains, and an inability to achieve the desired level of satisfaction from one's professional and personal endeavors are factors that can negatively impact an individual's well-being. When there is a discrepancy between the responsibilities and expectations associated with two or more roles that an individual occupies, the inability to fulfill these obligations or attain the desired level of satisfaction will also have an adverse effect on their well-being in other roles. The detrimental effects of work-related stressors on an individual's personal and social life can also have a negative impact on their work performance and experiences.

The concept of employee experience is unique to each individual employee. The employee's own evaluation of the experience is therefore the determining factor in the quality of the experience obtained. It is evident that the opportunities and working conditions on offer do not elicit the same level of satisfaction amongst all employees. It is essential to recognize that employee experience design should be approached with the understanding that it will appeal to every employee and that the employee should be placed at the center of the process. In order to enhance employee satisfaction and loyalty, it is essential to implement policies that align with this understanding, with the aim of attracting and retaining a qualified labor force.

In conclusion, the concepts of work-life balance, well-being and employee experience are inextricably linked. An unfavorable effect on one of these variables will create differences in the others.

It is recommended that human resources practices be implemented which will provide a positive and beneficial employee experience, thereby strengthening the relationship between work-life balance and well-being.

This study introduces a new research area, namely the examination of the role of employee experience in determining the impact of work-life balance on well-being. It is also anticipated that this study will contribute to the development of human resources policies as well.

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